

**INSTANT RELIEF FOR PAIN IN FROZEN SHOULDER W.S.R. TO AVABAHUKA (A
CASE SERIES)****Dr. Shruti Kuthe***

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Frozen shoulder is limiting function of the Glenohumeral joint. It is disabling disease of shoulder causing pain and restricted mobility of shoulder joint. It is characterized by severe pain in shoulder and restricted movement both active and passive. In textual references of Ayurveda Frozen Shoulder is closely related to *Avabahuka*. In modern science, aim of treatment is mainly focused on pain control, reduction of inflammation. For that steroidal and non steroidal anti inflammatory drugs are oftenly used which has their own side effects. In Ancient *Ayurveda*, various para-surgical procedures were mentioned like *viddhakarma*, *Agnikarma* which are classical Treatment for Pain Management described in *Sushruta Samhita*, are most widely Popular, cost effective, safe & instant pain relive in the management of *Avabahuka*. **Methodology:** A case of 3 patients presented with history of gradual onset of painful restricted movements of the shoulder joint with reduce Range of motion of shoulder joint The patients was diagnosed as a case of *Avabahuka* (Frozen Shoulder) Treatment given.

- 1) Four sittings of *Agnikarma* with swarna shalaka
- 2) *Trayodashang Guggulu* 3 tab after meal for TDS with *koshna jal*
- 3) *Sthanika swedan* - For 1 month

Objective Parameters

- 1) Gonio meter : for range of motion of shoulder joint
- 2) VAS Scale : measure for pain

Result: Before treatment – Range of motion of shoulder joint – 50° & VAS scale for pain – 5/10 After treatment - Range of motion of shoulder joint – 120° & VAS scale for pain – 8/10 the patients got relieved from pain and restricted shoulder joint movement along with improvement in complete abduction, flexion, extension, adduction, and external rotation by treated with *Agnikarma* and adjuvant medicines. **Conclusion:** From above case study, it has concluded that frozen shoulder w. s. r. *avabahuka* was characterised by severe pain in shoulder and restricted movement both active and passive which develops due to *vata- kapha* vriddhi. *Agnikarma* is classical treatment were mentioned for diseases of *Vata* and *Kapha*. Hence patients was treated with *Agnikarma* along with *adjuvant* drug gives significant relief in symptoms of frozon shoulder with special reference to *avabahuka*.

KEYWORDS: For that steroidal and non steroidal anti inflammatory drugs are oftenly used which has their own side effects.

INTRODUCTION

In Modern era, Due to expansion of competitions, people suffer from lots of diseases, it is actually hampering daily routine. Frozen shoulder is one of entity to hampers daily activity. It Incidence rate of this disease is 3-5% in general citizens. It increases up to 20% with diabetic patients. Next shoulder affected once first one has resolved in 6-17 % of patient.^[1]

Frozen shoulder clinically known as adhesive capsulitis^[2], is characterized by pain, stiffness, and limited function of the glenohumeral joint, which adversely affects the entire upper extremity. In this condition shoulder capsule becomes adherent to the humeral head that's why it is termed as "Adhesive capsulitis". The exact cause of this pathology remains elusive. There are two types identified are primary (idiopathic) and secondary. Idiopathic adhesive capsulitis

result from a chronic inflammatory response with fibroblastic proliferation, which may actually be an abnormal response from the immune system. Secondary adhesive capsulitis occurs after a shoulder injury or surgery, or may be associated with another condition such as diabetes, rotator cuff injury cerebrovascular accident. There are two principal characteristics of frozen shoulder- pain and contracture (loss of range of movement). Pain associated with it is progressive and initially felt mostly at night. The contracture of the shoulder ligaments decreases the volume of the capsule, thus limiting range of motion.^[3] The most common limitation in range of motion are flexion, abduction, and external rotation.^[4]

The normal course of frozen shoulder has as having three stages

Stage one: The “freezing” or painful stage, which may last from six weeks to nine months, & in which the patient has slow onset of pain. As the pain worsens, the shoulder loses motion.

Stage two: The “frozen” or adhesive stage is marked by slow improvement in pain but the stiffness remains. This stage generally lasts from four to nine months.

Stage three: The “thawing” or recovery, motion slowly returns towards normal. This generally last from 5 to 26 months.

Management of adhesive capsulitis by contemporary medicine mainly includes management of pain with analgesics and NSAIDs or sometime surgery is required. As far as modern medical science is concerned no promising management is available in Frozen Shoulder and when the disease condition become worse steroid therapy is advised which have more adverse effects and high economical cost.^[5]

On the basis of sign & symptoms this disease can be closely correlated with Avabahuka.^[6,7] Avabahuka is vata-kapha dominated disease. In this condition, Vata is localized in the shoulder region, getting aggravated, dries up the bindings (ligaments) of the shoulders, constricts the siras and produces Avabahuka.

Agnikarma is considered as best therapy to pacify vata-kapha doshas. Due to its Ushana, Sukshma, Ashukari guna. Therefore, vata-kapha pacifying management was planned for the present study. Agnikarma (Para-surgical

procedure) by the swarna shalaka^[8,9,10] in the management of frozen Shoulder is a new thrust area. swarna shalaka shows the action Shoth- har, kaphavatahar, shul-har and Anti-inflammatory activity, and also in the Ayurvedic literature description of Agni karma^[11,12,13] as Para-surgical procedure is a unique therapeutic procedure because of its preventive, primitive, prophylactic properties. With reference to Sushruta Samhita, Agni karma is advocated in joint disorders because of ushna guna and vata-kapha subsiding property of Agni. In this study swarna shalaka were used for Agnikarma, hence a study was proposed and attempt was made to evaluate Agni karma and its effect on Avabahuka.^[14,15,16]

CASE HISTORY

Patient information

A male patient age of 40 year visited to kayachikitsa OPD in shri k. r. pandav ayurved college and hospital with the complaints of pain and stiffness of left shoulder joint along with severe restriction of upward elevation of shoulder joints with reduce Range of motion of shoulder joint. Pain is constant in nature; He is unable to perform even small tasks due to restricted upward movement of limb. There was a history of treatment for frozen shoulder for last 3 months with no significant relief.

OBJECTIVES

Primary

To evaluate the effect of Agnikarma in Avabahuka with special reference to Frozen shoulder.

Secondary

1. To evaluate the improvement in the movements of shoulder.
2. To achieve immediate relief of pain in Frozen shoulder.

METHODOLOGY

- Selection of patients- Patients of Avabahuka fulfilling inclusion criteria.
- Duration of study- 21 Days for each patient.
- Follow up- on 0th, 7th, 14th and 21st day.
- Study location- OPD of kayachikitsa department , shri k. r. pandav ayurved college and hospital, nagpur

CLINICAL EXAMINATION

Dashvidha Pariksha

Prakriti	Vata Pittaja	Bala	Madhyam
Vikriti	Tridoshaja	Satyama	Madhyam
Sara	Avara	Satva	Madhyam
Samhana	Avara	Jarana Shakti	Avara
Vyayam Shakti	Avara	Ahara Shakti	Madham

General Physical Examination

B.P	130/80mmHg	RS	B/L equal air entry
P/R	74/min	CVS	S1 & S2 Normal
R/R	16/min	CNS	Conscious and well Oriented
Pallor	Absent	P/A	Soft & non-tender

Local Examination

- Muscle Power- 5/5 in both Upper & lower limb
- Muscle tone – Normal.
- Muscular Atrophy – Not present.
- Musculoskeletal System- Right Shoulder joint examination
- Swelling - mild Tenderness- +++

- 1) Four sittings of *Agnikarma* with swarna shalaka
- 2) *Trayodashang Guggulu* 3 tab after meal for TDS with *koshna jal*
- 3) *Sthanika swedan*-For 1 month

Procedure of Agnikarma

After taking written informed consent, Agnikarma was done by Swarna shalaka. The affected part was clean up with betadine. Agnikarma done by making multiple dots (Bindu Agnikarma) with Swarna shalaka covering Pain points. Appropriate precaution was taken not to produce *asamyak dagdha vrana*.^[17] After completion of the procedure there is no Agnikarma wound seen. The entire procedure was repeated three times at the interval of 7 days.

Restriction of range of movement

- Adduction- 00
- Abduction- 60⁰
- Flexion – 60⁰
- Extension -20⁰

Investigation: - X-ray left shoulder joint suggests no any significant bony abnormality.

TREATMENT

After careful assessment and examination, patients were treated with.

Assessment criteria

Assessment is done on the basis of scoring before and after treatment. Scoring of Symptoms.

1. Bahupraspandithara

Can do work without being affected	0
Can do strenuous work with difficulty	1
Can do daily routine work with great difficulty	2
Cannot do any work	3

2. Shoola

No pain at all	0
Mild pain can do strenuous work with difficulty	1
Moderate pain can do normal work with support	2
Severe pain, unable to do any work at all	3

3. Amsashosha

No wasting	0
Mild wasting	1
Moderate wasting	2
Severe wasting	3

Assessment of pain & Range of movement**1. Pain (Amsa Sandhi Shoola) was assessed by Visual Analogue scale (0–10scale)**

Vas score	
Grade Table	Tenderness
0	No pain
1-3	Mild pain
4-7	Moderate pain
8-10	Severe pain

2. Range Of Movement

Movement	Normal Range
Flexion	180
Extension	60
Abduction	180

Internal rotation	90
External rotation	90

OBSERVATION AND RESULT

After 4 sittings of Agnikarma with tribhuvankirti rasa were done after 21 days (every 7 days interval), all

patients got miraculous results in pain and motion with almost 95 percent relief.

Patient → Symptoms ⇩	1		2		3	
	BT	AT	BT	AT	BT	AT
Bahuprasapandithara	3	0	3	0	3	0
Shoola	2	1	2	0	3	1
Amshashosha	1	0	2	1	2	0
Adduction	50	50	40	40	30	40
Abduction	90	120	120	140	110	140
Flexion	120	160	100	170	110	150
Extension	30	50	40	60	50	50
Internal rotation	60	90	50	80	50	90
External rotation	60	90	50	90	50	60

Vas Score before and after treatment

Before treatment	At 7 th day	At 14 th day	At 21 st day
8- severe pain	7- moderate pain	4- mild pain	1- mild pain occasionally

DISCUSSION

Frozen shoulder is disabling disease of shoulder and is self-limiting, but recovery takes much longer time up to 3-4 yrs. Many treatment options are available for management of frozen shoulder still there is no consensus in literature regarding which therapeutic option is superior mostly because of lack of high level of evidence. As the recovery period is much longer and initial stage of freezing is very painful some alternative treatment like ayurveda is very beneficial. Agnikarma is unique procedure described in ayurveda for instant relief from pain. It has been mentioned in the Ayurveda literature (Shushrut Samhita) diseases cured by agnikarma never recur.^[11,12] Agnikarma is indicated in all painful condition which are due to vata and pitta. Frozen shoulder can be correlated with Avabahuka as per ayurveda. Agnikarma is indicated in avabahuka (i.e.frozen shoulder). Vata and kapha both are involved in the pathology of frozen shoulder. Swarna shalaka Agnikarma immediately results in pacification of vata and kapha. This gives immediate improvement in symptoms of frozen shoulder. Like there is significant reduction in pain and stiffness resulting in increasing range of mobility. In present case patient got 70% relief in pain on first day immediately after agnikarma but from 2 nd day pain increased; however, pain was less than previous pain as it was before. Swarna shalaka agnikarma. Swarna shalaka heated till it became warm when it was applied to most tender spot it must have reached to the dipper pathological part of shoulder joint (i.e., joint capsule) there by relieving inflammation and hence resulted in reduction of pain. As the pain was reduced patient himself felt confident, this resulted in improvement in range of movement. Application of Swarna shalaka itself reduces pain. This is probable

mode of action of Swarna shalaka agnikarma procedure in relieving the symptoms, this fact influences theories in pain research, the gate-control theory^[18,19] published almost 50 years ago. Simply, this theory states that the transmission of pain from the peripheral nervous system is subjected to modulation in the spinal cord. The major cell type controlled by this gate are the wide dynamic range (WDR) neurons of the dorsal horn of the spinal cord, the region to which sensory information is conveyed. One of the elements of this modulation is the input from large sensory nerve fibers activated by touch. Through an inhibitory circuit in the spinal cord, these fibers can inhibit the firing of WDR neurons and “closed the gate”, therefore inhibiting the transmission of nociceptive inputs. This results in reducing pain. Swarna shalaka Agnikarma works on same principle. Agnikarma results in dilatation of local capillaries which results in improvement of blood supply to the part this results in sweeping away the inflammatory substances. However, if the disease is chronic, inflammation may not subside in single sitting.

Aim of treatment in frozen shoulder is to reduce pain and to increase range of mobility. This can be achieved by reducing inflammation. Agnikarma is a type of mild fomentation this results in reduction in inflammation. Swarna shalaka itself has an anti-inflammatory activity. Patient got sustained relief in pain. As the pain was reduced patient was able to do gentle stretching exercises. Gentle stretching exercises within the limit of pain achieves more mobility than aggressive stretching exercise. It results in pacification of vata. it has ushna virya (i.e., hot in action). Vata is having sheeta virya (having cold action). Hot property of Swarna shalaka acts opposite to cold property of vata and kapha. It can

be used in various condition where vata and kapha is involved. In the present case both pain, stiffness was due to mainly vata and kapha, Vitiating of vata and kapha are the etiological factors in frozen shoulder so Swarna shalaka works better in this ailment. Thus, in present case we got excellent result by Swarna shalaka agnikarma, as vata and kapha are the causative factors, this therapy resulted in pacification of vata and kapha thereby giving significant relief in symptoms.

Mode of Action of Agnikarma

Frozen Shoulder (Avbhauka) is produced by vitiated vata dosha with anubandha of kapha, so Agnikarma is considered as best therapy to pacify these doshas. Due to Ushna, Sukshma, Ashukari guna it pacifies vitiated vata-kapha dosha. Pain receptors are located in the skin and the motor end plates of the muscles. These pain receptors are stimulated by application of heat. Pathway for transmission of thermal signals and pain signals are almost parallel, but terminate at same area. So out of these two i.e. thermal and pain only the stronger one can be felt, so on therapeutic application of heat, relief of pain can be explained by complete exclusion of pain impulses by heat impulses due to occupying a final pathway.

CONCLUSION

From above case study, it has concluded that frozen shoulder w. s. r. *avabahuka* was characterised by severe pain in shoulder and restricted movement both active and passive which develops due to *vata- kapha* vriddhi. *Agnikarma* is classical treatment were mentioned for diseases of *Vata* and *Kapha*. Hence patients was treated with *Agnikarma* along with *adjuvent* drug gives significant relief in symptoms of frozon shoulder with special reference to *avabahuka*. No adverse effect was observed during the course of treatment. The treatment applied was simple, economical and required no hospitalization and could be done at OPD level.

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